

Starting the process

Guidelines on governance settings
for responsible and open science

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

FOSTERING IMPROVED
TRAINING TOOLS FOR
RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH
AND INNOVATION

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A scene of rapid change

What is at stake

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and Open Science (OS) have been increasingly proposed to scientists and research organisations as the new governance framework for science. There is increased social and policy pressure to make science **fully embedded in society** and therefore involved in and responsible for the impacts it produces on the economy and society at large, as well as open to external actors (government, industry, civil society, the public at large) and sensitive towards expectations, needs, worries and problems of present in the social context.

However, **this process is not free of problems, uncertainties, and risks**. Research organisations and research systems are already exposed to strong processes of change, originating both from the inside and the outside, which are modifying their culture, procedures, decision mechanisms and organisational structure.

Consequently, while researchers and stakeholders perceive that the usual governance structure and the ordinary practices related to scientific production are weakening, they are also uncertain about what will occur next.

The aim of the Guidelines

These Guidelines are intended to deal with this complex set of issues, starting from a simple question: **how to effectively embed RRI and OS in research organisations?**

The Guidelines do not purport to offer ready-made solutions to this problem since ready-made solutions simply do not exist. Rather, its main aim is to propose a pathway for activating institutional change processes towards RRI and OS in research organisations.

The focus on governance

In this perspective, a key concept which will be used in the Guidelines will be that of **governance setting**. This expression refers to a coordinated set of actions serving as a starter to implement RRI and OS or part of them in a given research organisation. Therefore, the focus of the Guidelines is on the first steps to take for creating in the research organisation the minimal conditions necessary to ensure that an evolutionary process towards RRI/OS can take place.

Guiding the process

The Guidelines of governance settings, available online (fit4rri.eu/) and summarized here, provide information, orientations and recommendations for guiding this process and, in particular, for:

- Interpreting RRI and OS
- Identifying and taking the basic decisions to activate the governance setting process
- Activating, implementing and finalising such process to produce long-term institutional changes in research organisations.

The project and the experiments

The Guidelines are one of the main products of the project “Fostering Improved Training Tools for Responsible Research and Innovation - FIT4RRI”, co-funded by the EU DG Research and Innovation under Horizon 2020 and coordinated by Sapienza University of Rome. Some of the orientations reported in the Guidelines have been tested in **four experiments** carried out in the framework of FIT4RRI, coordinated by the South-East European Research Centre (SEERC) and conducted respectively at the Instituto de Soldadura e Qualidade – ISQ (Portugal), the University of Liverpool (UK), the Sapienza University of Rome (Italy) and the Open University (UK).

GUIDELINES FOR INTERPRETATION

CHANGES IN SCIENCE

Science and innovation are affected by a **wide range of changes**. Being aware of features, contents, and trajectories of these changes is extremely important to approach RRI and OS properly.

An emerging social model for science

Various interpretive models (e.g., Mode 1 - Mode 2 Model, Post-academic science, Triple or Quadruple Helix Model, Post-normal science) have been developed to account for these changes. Although different from each other, they overall define an **emerging “social model” for science**, recognising it as:

- Fully embedded in society and connected with political, economic, and societal dynamics
- Open to the external actors Sensitive towards expectations, needs, worries and problems of society
- Able to develop forms of co-direction and co-production with stakeholders and the public at large
- Concerned with the actual implications and use of its outputs
- Increasingly involved with innovation and with producing social and economic benefits, and based on interdisciplinary approaches.

Such emerging model tends to overcome the consolidated social model of science – sometimes symbolically associated with the image of the “Ivory Tower” – which defines science as substantially autonomous from society, internally organised in well-defined disciplinary fields, not involved in the actual implications and use of its outputs (in terms of knowledge, discoveries, technologies, but also impacts and risks) and proceeding mainly on the basis of the interests of scientists.

Critical transformations

This transition of science towards a new social model – due to a general shift occurring in society from modernity to late modernity – is now rapidly evolving. However, it is not occurring smoothly and linearly. A wide range of **critical transformations** are occurring, which are directly or indirectly linked with this shift from a social model of science to another.

The increasing competition among researchers and research organisations on a global scale is leading to an acceleration of the research processes, with impacts on the organisation of academic life, the researchers' living conditions, the quality of research, and research integrity. Peer-reviewing procedures and research evaluation are more and more questioned in terms of both methods and outputs. A crisis in the capacity of scientists to reproduce and reuse research data is also emerging. The organisation of science as a community of peers is fading away while an "industrial" organisational approach is emerging, leading to an increased segmentation of staff (by age, sex, nationality, and contractual status), with effects like overtraining and overexploitation of young researchers, decrease in teaching quality, and an increased attitude of self-promotion among scientists.

Key issues

Before dealing with RRI and OS, research leaders and managers need to understand:

- How these changes are affecting their organisation and with what effects
- How the changes are perceived by the staff (researchers, managers, leaders, students, etc.)
- How the organisation leaders or individual staff members react and attempt to manage them.

A RESPONSIBLE AND OPEN SCIENCE

It is in this context of change that Responsible Research and Innovation and Open Science are to be placed in as much as they can provide research organisations with knowledge and tools, which could be helpful for managing the transformation of science.

Responsible Research and Innovation

The concept of **Responsible Research and Innovation** has, at its core, the idea that science actors should be responsible, in close interaction with other societal actors, of the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the scientific knowledge and its economic and social impacts. In the view of the European Commission, RRI includes five keys or pillars (i.e., gender equality, public engagement, research ethics and integrity, science education, and open access), and four dimensions (i.e., anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion, and responsiveness) which could be useful for guiding the process of change.

Open Science

The concept of **Open Science** is more focused on the research process. It emerges as a progressive enlargement of the principles of open access, i.e., making sure that publicly funded research outputs are accessible to all. While the idea of "openness" was initially limited to scientific publications, it is now increasingly used with reference to many other products (e.g., data, software) and processes (e.g., peer-review) up to define highly-colaborative practices affecting all the aspects of science and innovation.

Barriers to RRI and OS

Although different from each other, the two concepts are partially overlapped and are both based on a common view of making science more efficient and open to societal and economic needs and expectations. However, although experiences and practices inspired by RRI and OS are multiplying, different **barriers** to their development are still there. Implementing RRI and OS requires complex institutional change processes to modify consolidated structures, practices, culture and procedures. It is not surprising that these processes usually generate resistance, tensions or simply organisational stress. Moreover, RRI and OS are interpreted in different ways, so that a common view is not always simple to achieve. Finally, RRI and OS are often overlooked by researchers and research managers or perceived by them as something producing time-consuming obligations and tasks which add up to the ordinary (already highly absorbing) activities.

Key issues

Hence the importance for research institutions to understand how and under which conditions RRI and OS can be usefully applied in a given specific research organisation. In this regard, three key issues should be considered:

- Which are the actions and strategies already in place or planned to promote RRI and OS in the organisation and how they work
- To what extent staff and leaders express a consent towards RRI and OS
- Which are the external actors and stakeholders the organisation is already working with to carry out RRI and OS.

GUIDELINES FOR DECISION

DEFINING THE RRI/OS PROFILE

The next step is taking the necessary decisions to define an RRI/OS profile tailored on **the specific** features and needs of **any given** research organisation. There are no established procedures in this regard. Each organisation should find its **own** way. However, it can be useful to clarify **some of the components** which come into play in this decision process.

Institutional changes

Deciding on RRI and OS necessarily means making a diagnosis to understand whether, how and why activating RRI/OS-oriented **institutional changes** within the organisation. Institutional changes can be understood as irreversible changes inspired to RRI and OS affecting the way in which the research organisation, inter alia, makes research, organises its internal life, decides, defines its objectives or interacts with external actors.

Benefit and drivers

In making the diagnosis, it is important to get some ideas about the expected **benefits of RRI and OS for the organisation** (for example, increasing the quality of research and innovation, supporting a democratization of decision-making process, preventing forms of exploita-

tion of young researchers, involving people and stakeholders in the research and innovation process, increasing and accelerating the social and economic impacts of research, etc.) and the **potential drivers** which can facilitate their implementation (policy measures, incentives, or mechanisms supporting RRI and OS, the use of RRI and OS to access more resources or to accelerate innovation, the attention towards ethical issues and responsibility, etc.).

Scale and scope

It is also important to take into consideration the **scale** and the **scope** of the RRI/OS profile. The **scale** concerns the parts of the organisation which are involved in the process of change. For example, a small pilot programme can be launched involving only some units of the organisation and then enlarging the process up to cover the entire organisation or, conversely, a programme directly involving the organisation as a whole can be promoted to be then adapted to the needs of individual departments. The **scope** concerns the components of RRI or OS **considered** in the governance setting process. For example, only some specific aspects of Open Science or one key of RRI (gender equality, public engagement, etc.) can be initially addressed to then enlarge the scope to RRI or OS as a whole or, conversely, a policy action embracing RRI or Open Science as a whole can be launched to then develop specific actions for each key.

Key issues

Dealing with RRI/OS self-tailored profile, at least three key issues should be touched:

- Why the organisation should start a process of institutional change based on RRI and OS
- Which are the priority areas for RRI and OS, to achieve which goals and to manage which risks
- Which constraints and obstacles should be considered before starting the process.

CHOOSING THE GOVERNANCE SETTING

Another issue to consider in the decision process is **how to start** the process of institutional embedment of RRI and OS in the organisation.

The concept of governance setting

It is at this point that the very concept of governance setting comes to play. As we said above, it refers to a short-term programme or a set of actions serving as a starter for longer-term institutional changes towards RRI and OS in the organisation.

Types of governance setting

Based on an empirical analysis carried out under FIT4RRI on around 300 cases of programmes and projects targeting RRI and OS, two variables have been identified distinguishing governance settings:

- **Who starts and manages the process of change**, i.e., the organisation itself, an external organisation (like a consultancy firm or a funding organization) or a network of actors the organisation is part of.
- **Which aspects of an organisation the governance setting addresses first**, i.e., the social patterns (behaviours, cultural attitudes, etc.) of staff and leaders, the norms (procedures, guidelines, structures, etc.) regulating the life of the organisation or the practices adopted in the organization in producing scientific knowledge.

Crossing these two variables, a typology of governance settings can be developed, identifying three cases for the first variable (internally-initiated, externally-initiated, and network-initiated model) and three cases for the second variable (social, normative, and knowledge-oriented model). Rarely a governance setting process fully falls into a specific type and mixed situations are common. Nonetheless, the typology could help take appropriate decisions about the **best general strategy** to devise for starting the institutional change process in the organisation. Some examples are given below.

GOVERNANCE SETTING MODELS	EXAMPLES OF ACTIONS
Internally-initiated social model	Development of RRI/OS-oriented internal action plans based on the mobilisation of internal and external stakeholders; internal awareness-raising and training programme on RRI/OS
Internally-initiated normative model	Adoption of new internal regulations, procedures, guidelines developed by the organisations' leadership; establishment of internal RRI-oriented research funding criteria
Internally-initiated knowledge-oriented model	Establishment of a new research unit focused on RRI/OS-related issues; activation of RRI/OS-focused research programmes by the research organisation
Externally-initiated social model	Use of external RRI/OS experts; participation in national/international RRI/OS-oriented programmes
Externally-initiated normative model	RRI/OS-oriented certification processes
Externally-initiated knowledge-oriented model	RRI/OS-oriented national research funding schemes
Network-initiated social model	Participation of the organisation in RRI/OS-specialised networks; participation of the organisation in cross-institutional RRI-oriented programmes
Network-initiated normative model	The organisation signing up to a network-based charter (such as the UK Athena-SWAN Chartered, aimed at supporting research organisations in developing a gender equality action plan)
Network-initiated knowledge-oriented model	Establishment within the organisation of RRI/OS-focused research units or research programmes supported by a pool, network, or association of research institutions

Key issues

For selecting the most appropriate governance setting for the organisation, three key issues should be taken in mind:

- To what extent the organisation is equipped for autonomously activating or accelerating the institutional embedment of RRI and OS (if the answer is negative, an externally-initiated model or a network-initiated model should be more appropriate)
- Which aspects of the organisation's life can be more easily modified in a short-term perspective and with less effort
- Which opportunities, internal or external to the organisation, can be seized for developing an effective governance setting (for example, the opportunity to apply for research funds connected to RRI or OS, the presence of researchers already skilled in RRI/OS activities, or the presence of policies or incentives to RRI and OS).

GUIDELINES FOR ACTION

ACTIVATING THE GOVERNANCE SETTING PROCESS

The main character of governance settings is variability. Many factors come into play producing different or even diverging situations. It is therefore difficult to say what exactly it takes to start the process. Nonetheless, at least three **critical factors** can be highlighted.

A guiding idea

The first factor is the presence of a **guiding idea** around which the governance setting process can be structured. Defining a guiding idea is necessary to provide motivations to act and mobilising internal and external stakeholders on RRI and OS. Examples of guiding ideas can be “Identifying the ethical and societal aspects of technological innovations at an early stage that these can be considered in the design process”, “Democratising innovation to create a more equitable and inclusive capability to solve problems using science and technology” or “Promoting social responsibility and community involvement of students and teachers and integrating these issues into university teaching”. Defining the guiding idea is a useful exercise for a better understanding of what RRI and OS can be and the role they can play for improving the research organisation.

An effective team

Another key factor is the **team** which will drive the governance setting process. The team serves multiple key functions, such as making it possible an institutional learning process, motivating the actors to be mobilised, coping with resistances and constraints, keeping the direction of change or timely changing it when necessary, and negotiating with all the actors involved. Creating a skilled, cohesive and motivated team is, therefore, an aspect not to be overlooked which takes time and engagement.

The support from leaders and managers

The **support from leaders and managers** is another important factor to consider. It usually has different positive effects such as producing a symbolic impact on staff, facilitating the decision-making process, showing the involvement of leaders as champions of RRI and OS, connecting RRI/OS with the mission of the organisation or managing resistances. On the contrary, the lack of support represents a serious obstacle for the implementation of any action aimed to RRI and OS, entailing, for example, conflicts, waste of time or problems in accessing resources.

Key issues

Who starts a governance setting process faces a series of questions that need to be treated carefully. At least three of them deserve to be mentioned here:

- To what extent the commitment of leaders and managers to the development of the governance setting process is strong and visible
- To what extent the governance setting process could be based on volunteering (RRI and OS cannot be considered as fully based on volunteering and therefore a professional core team is necessary, even though forms of voluntary mobilisation are equally necessary)
- How to create effective communication and cooperation among the involved actors.

IMPLEMENTING THE GOVERNANCE SETTING PROCESS

Implementing a governance setting process means **turning ideas and plans** elaborated in the previous phases into new practices, approaches, and views. Each organisation must find its way to do it.

The process of change

It is to keep in mind that institutional changes tend to develop through a set of steps. **Different models** have been elaborated about how the implementation process of RRI and OS is expected to occur.

For example, the model developed by the FOTRRIS project identifies four steps in RRI-oriented actions: i) the destabilisation of the regime (e.g., institutionalised organisations, interactions, rules, beliefs, routines, visions); ii) the experimentation of RRI-based alternatives; iii) the phasing-out the non-RRI-based elements of the system; iv) the institutionalisation of RRI-based alternatives.

Under the STAGES project, focusing on gender equality in science, a four-step model was developed: i) the creation of a “transformational agent”, i.e., a team able to activate a process of change; ii) the mobilisation and involvement of key stakeholders (e.g., researchers, leaders, management units, external networks, etc.), so to gain their active support; iii) the design and activation of initiatives and actions aimed at modifying the organisation, dealing with resistances and facing technical, cultural or organisational obstacles; iv) the establishment of new institutional arrangements and organisational solutions (new rules, structures, norms, agreements, recurrent initiatives, etc.) to make the new changes sustainable over time.

The key role of negotiation

Whatever be the model of change adopted, it is quite clear that activating an institutional change process primarily means activating a set of **negotiations** among the many actors involved. Negotiation is a sort of iterative process progressively moving the process of change ahead and weakening consolidated procedures, practices and rules. Different **dimensions of negotiation** are involved in institutional change, including:

- The **interpretive dimension** (concerning the interpretation of the problems to be dealt with and how RRI and OS could help cope with them)
- The **symbolic dimension** (concerning the visibility and attractiveness of RRI and OS within the organisation)
- The **institutional dimension** (concerning the new institutional solutions to be introduced)
- The **operational dimension** (concerning the actual implementation of decisions already made and therefore the actual possibility to have things done effectively and in a reasonable time).

Monitoring and evaluation

Another key role in the governance setting process is played by the establishment and use of **monitoring and evaluation mechanisms** about RRI and OS, which should be appropriate to the nature and contents of the governance setting process.

Key issues

Implementing the governance setting primarily means being pro-active in promoting the governance setting process and reactive or even anticipatory in preventing obstacles and seizing emerging opportunities. Three key issues can be highlighted in this regard:

- How to create spaces for engagement and mobilisation (such as networks, committees, research groups, virtual platforms) allowing to turn passion, interest and willingness to participate into actual participation
- How to prevent a “saturation effect” about RRI and OS, i.e., the sensation of stakeholders and researchers that RRI and OS are “saturating” their time, thus generating negative reactions or even the refusal of getting involved with RRI and OS
- How to ensure continuity in the governance setting process, preventing the risk that, e.g., people in the organization feel that nothing is happening or, after a while, start “forgetting” RRI and OS.

COMPLETING THE GOVERNANCE SETTING PROCESS

The governance setting can be viewed as a “special programme” destined to be ended in a reasonable lapse of time to pave the way to long-term RRI/OS-oriented mechanisms. In this sense, we could define the completion of the governance setting process as a **transition phase**, in which RRI and Open Science start being managed through the ordinary structures and procedures of the research organisations.

Sustainability plan

The transition phase of the governance setting process should be guided by some sort of sustainability plan, i.e., a plan establishing how RRI and OS are expected to evolve in the future in the research organisation. In developing a sustainability plan, some basic issues should be considered, such as:

- Defining a new governance structure or a new team responsible for RRI and OS in the research organization
- Identifying the action lines which are more appropriate for RRI and OS to be sustainable
- Verifying if in the organisation there are the expertise and management capacity necessary for implementing RRI and OS
- Assessing the human, organisational and technical resources needed
- Establishing monitoring and evaluation mechanisms for ensuring a quality assessment of the RRI/OS-related actions
- Verifying if there is comprehensive and sufficient support by the leaders and managers.

Institutional arrangement

The plan should also describe the **institutional arrangements** ensuring the long-term sustainability of the actions initiated during the governance setting process and those to be developed in the future. Examples of institutional arrangements are:

- Establishment of permanent agreements with external stakeholders
- Creation of awards and forms of recognition related to RRI and OS
- Periodical collection of relevant data (for example, on gender dynamics, on the use of open access publications, on the diffusion of public engagement in the organisation)
- Allocation of funds on RRI and OS-related activities
- Establishment of new organisational structures or appointment of new officers (e.g., ethics committees, gender equality officer, open science department, public engagement office)
- Establishment of new physical infrastructures (Open access repository, co-working spaces for favouring public engagement, kindergartens inside the organisation, etc.)
- Establishment of new regulations, standards, and procedures (e.g., new guidelines to develop gender-fair recruitment procedures, new procedures concerning publications, new criteria in research funds allocation allowing the involvement of external stakeholders)
- Organisation of annual events (conferences, galas, theatrical events, etc.)
- Development of new training modules
- Creating new web-based structures (webpages, websites, blogs, web-based platforms and other forms of institutional communication)

Key issues

About the completion of the governance setting process, three key issues can be identified:

- How to integrate the different RRI keys (e.g., gender equality, research ethics and integrity, or public engagement), the different aspects of the Open Science (e.g., open access to publications, open data, or open science evaluation) and, more in general, how to integrate RRI with Open Science

- How to foster mobilisation over time so that RRI and OS remain a priority in the organisation's agenda
- Which risks should be considered before closing the governance setting process (for example, risks related to the bureaucratisation of the activities, the slowing down of the process, the diminishing visibility of the issues related to RRI and OS or the lack of motivation of those who take on the institutional responsibility of RRI/OS-related programmes).

List of recommendations

A set of recommendations – organised following the structure of the Guidelines – have been developed to help research organisations interested in implementing RRI and OS.

CHANGES IN SCIENCE

- 1.** Mapping the main trends of change affecting one's research organisation
- 2.** Fostering an internal debate on the changes occurring in science and the measures to address them
- 3.** Establishing tools for monitoring and anticipating the trends of change affecting the organisation

A RESPONSIBLE AND OPEN SCIENCE

- 4.** Making an inventory of and assessing the actions and measures already in place or planned pertaining to RRI and OS
- 5.** Identifying people and resources already involved with or interested in RRI and OS
- 6.** Raising awareness and disseminating knowledge on RRI and OS among leaders, managers and staff

DEFINING THE RRI/OS PROFILE

- 7.** Defining the RRI/OS profile for the organisation through an open decision-making process
- 8.** Documenting the decision-making process and its results to make them accessible to everyone
- 9.** Keeping a process-like view of the RRI/OS profile and following an open and step-by-step approach

CHOOSING THE GOVERNANCE SETTING

- 10.** Choosing the governance setting model primarily on the basis of feasibility considerations
- 11.** Scrutinising external resources to learn from
- 12.** Testing the governance setting before starting the process

ACTIVATING THE GOVERNANCE SETTING PROCESS

- 13.** Establishing a team which is substantially and institutionally capable to activate the governance setting process
- 14.** Ensuring the transparency, inclusiveness and visibility of the governance setting process
- 15.** Making RRI and OS part of the “core business” of the research organisation from the beginning

IMPLEMENTING THE GOVERNANCE SETTING PROCESS

- 16.** Activating negotiation processes within the organisation aimed at modifying current practices, rules, and views
- 17.** Looking for external backing and links to enhance the governance setting process
- 18.** Adopting an iterative approach in implementing the governance setting process

COMPLETING THE GOVERNANCE SETTING PROCESS

- 19.** Carefully planning and implementing the changeover of RRI/OS from the governance setting to the structures of the organisation
- 20.** Including RRI and Open Science in the organisational standards and practices following a mainstreaming approach
- 21.** Creating social and communication spaces and procedures to maintain a high degree of participation in RRI and Open Science

